

The Institutes of John Cassian

By Joshua Schachterle, Independent Scholar

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Monasticism, Christian monasticism, Latin Text

Originally titled *The Institutes of the Cenobia and the Remedies for the Eight Principal Vices*, this document was written in the 5th century by a monk named John Cassian in order to help found a monastery in the Roman-controlled region of Gaul (modern-day France). Cassian's instructions on how to correctly practice monasticism on both the practical and spiritual levels were based on his experience living as a monk in Egypt, one of the cradles of Christian monasticism. First chapters include teachings on how monks should dress, pray, and work on a daily basis. The remaining chapters instruct monks on how to deal with the eight principal vices, which would later be renumbered and renamed as the seven deadly sins. The book, along with the second volume known as the *Conferences*, would come to have a long history. It brought the traditions of Egyptian monasticism to the West and influenced Benedict of Nursia's monastic rule deeply, which would, in turn, impact the entire history of Western monasticism.

Date Range: 420 CE - 430 CE

Region: Massilia, Gaul

Region tags: Europe, Gaul

Region on the southern Mediterranean coast of the Roman province of Gaul (modern day Marseille, France).

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Translated by Boniface Ramsey. *John Cassian: The Institutes*. Ancient Christian Writers, 58. New York, NY: The Newman Press, 2000.
- Source 2: Columba Stewart. *Cassian the Monk*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1998.
- Source 3: , Joshua Daniel Schachterle. "Exercising Obedience: John Cassian and the Creation of Early Monastic Subjectivity." Dissertation, N.p., 2019

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/3507.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Cassian's Institutes online
- Source 2 URL: http://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/02m/0360-0435,_Cassianus_loannes,_De_Coenobiorum_Institutis_Libri_Duodecim,_MLT.pdf

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: While we don't know anything about where the material text was kept, it was read out loud daily during and after meals in the monasteries of Benedict of Nursia, who considered it one of the most edifying writings for monks outside of Scripture. It must therefore have been kept in a privileged place.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: While it was not funded by any civil government, the text was commissioned and, presumably, paid for by Bishop Castor of Apta Julia in Gaul, so it was, in a sense, funded by the "polity" of the Gallican church.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: We don't know about its reception in its time. However, it would later become so foundational to Benedict's rule for monks and monasteries in Western Europe that one might call it a religious text, although certainly not scripture.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: While it is not a sacred text, per se, it does describe the correct methods for ritual worship and/or prayer.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Institutes was written as the first volume of a two-volume work, the second being the Conferences. Both are aimed at bringing the monastic traditions of Egypt to the Western Roman Empire.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: However, given its privileged status in many monasteries, the Institutes clearly did become part of a canon of non-scriptural texts used for the edification of monks.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

–Specify: The Institutes is the first volume and generally addresses the practical life of the monk while The Conferences is the second volume and addresses the theology and spirituality of monastic life.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: It is the first to explicitly explain and advocate for using the monastic traditions of Egypt in monasteries in the West.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: Cassian frequently emphasizes that the monks of Egypt do monasticism correctly while those he's observed in Gaul are getting it all wrong. Subsequent monasteries in the West will thus try to adapt the traditions of Egyptian monasticism to their own context.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: This text prescribes daily behaviors for monks in almost every possible context. It sets the bar for correct behavior very high for monks.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?

(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text specifies the times that certain Psalms or prayers are to be offered, the number of such prayers and psalms, and how prayer services are to be conducted.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Cassian believes that there is only one correct way to live in a monastery: the way Egyptian monks live. He is therefore attempting to establish Egyptian traditions as part of a lineage he hopes will continue in the West. In fact, he asserts that Egyptian traditions can be traced back to Elijah, John the Baptist, and the apostles.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The chain of authority is not titular, in the sense of a priest or a bishop, but rather one based upon ascetic practice. Those who correctly practice asceticism as the Egyptian monks apparently do, are the authorities. Of course, this includes himself.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Notes: The text asserts that the monks of Egypt are the only ones who have the requisite authority to define correct monastic practice. According to the text, the correct performance of monastic ritual was taught to these original monks by an angel. Monks like Cassian himself who practice assiduous asceticism are worthy of passing down authority by teaching these correct practices.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: There are many rules to be followed in the text, but it would be misleading to call these "legal code."

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The "calendar" is simply a day to day schedule of practices that must be done according to the instruction of the author's teachers in Egypt.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The soul is the higher part of the human being, while the body is what limits the soul through its needs and desires. Asceticism is the method of diminishing the needs of the body and elevating the soul.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

Notes: While the spirit is ontologically distinct from the body, it is material, though made of a substance much more highly refined than crude matter.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

Notes: Denying the body its desires is believed, in this text and others of its time, to elevate the soul.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Notes: Negative psychological states such as depression or anger are often viewed as demonic attacks. Even sly suggestions of evil thoughts or lust are seen as attacks which monks must learn to repel.

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: Monastics according to this text generally accept mind/body or soul/body dualism. Through ascetic practice, the body, often characterized as an unruly child, is brought under submission to the mind/soul.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: Yes with a qualification: the soul, while able to be ultimately separated from the body, was formed of a kind of highly refined matter. Thus while modern thinkers might characterize a soul as wholly immaterial, this would not quite be accurate in Late Antiquity.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The author encourages monks to frequently contemplate both the heavenly rewards of virtuous behavior on earth and the torturous consequences of misbehavior.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Corpses are to be buried, presumably in preparation for a general resurrection at a non-specified time in the future.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to angels, especially as bringers of correct practices to earlier monks in Egypt. This establishes the authority of the practices Cassian is bringing to the monks in Gaul.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Obviously, Christian monks believe in a supreme high god. However, God does not speak directly in the text, but rather conveys his will through the agency of angels.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: There are several references to angels teaching the correct methods of prayer and psalmody to the early monks.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: There is one story in which a man arises spontaneously during communal prayer and leads the chant, after which he disappears. This prompts them to believe that the man was an angel.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The angels mentioned in the Institutes seem only to have knowledge of correct monastic practice.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: Only to correct monastic practice, especially the forms of communal prayer.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: The angel mentioned is only seen among Egyptian monks, demonstrating the divine authority granted to the monks of that region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

Notes: Since there is only one occurrence of the appearance of an angel, it is difficult to know within this text what the angel can or can't see.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: This can be presumed based on other concurrent monastic literature but is not explicit in this text.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Again, teaching correct prayer methods has a direct effect on the monks who teach the methods to the following generations down to Cassian's time.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– No

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Yes

Notes: See the above notes on monks being taught by an anthropomorphic angel.

↳ In waking, everyday life?
– Yes

Notes: Again, the only appearance in this text is during waking life.

↳ In dreams?
– No

↳ In trance possession?
– No

↳ Through divination practices?
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?
– No

↳ Only through monarch?
– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

Notes: Causal efficacy is only through example and thus direct communication.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– No

Notes: No emotion is exhibited by the angel in this text.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: This text merely describes an earlier appearance. The text does not invoke the angel, nor is it designed to do so.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The story in which the angel teaches prayer to the monks assumes that the deity is monitoring and thus correcting the monks.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Notes: Since the angel seems to care only about prayer, there is no indication that other rules are directly given by the deity.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: While this text does discuss the requirement of celibacy for monks, it does not come directly from the angel.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Notes: Certainly the author cares about this and many other moral requirements, but there is no direct evidence for the deity's hand in this in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Notes: Certainly the author cares about this and many other moral requirements, but there is no direct evidence for the deity's hand in this in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Notes: Certainly the author cares about this and many other moral requirements, but there is no direct evidence for the deity's hand in this in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: An angel teaches the number of prayers and their order in the monastic liturgy.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: An angel teaches the number of prayers and their order in the monastic liturgy.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: While there are references to the afterlife, both rewards and punishments, and this likely depends on early Christian views of eschatology, this does not appear explicitly in the text.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The vast majority of these norms concern the performance of prayer rituals. The second volume of Cassian's work deal a bit more with social norms.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: There is a constant implication that those who are proper monks, defined as living ascetically according to the traditions of Egypt, are morally superior to both incorrectly practicing monks and to laypeople.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Chapters 5-12 address the 8 principal vices (gluttony, fornication, avarice, anger, sadness, acedia, vainglory, and pride) and how to counteract them when they arise within the mind and heart of a monk.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Notes: Achieving unity with God is tied to rejection of 8 principal vices. In addition, the arising of the vices within a monk's heart and mind are viewed as demonic attacks.

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

Notes: The vices are vaguely characterized as demonic.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only specialized religious class

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No

- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
 - ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
 - ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
 - ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
 - ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
 - ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No
 - ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
 - ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
 - ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
 - ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
 - ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No
 - ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes
- Notes: The most important virtue is ascetic renunciation.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: This is explicitly addressed in the chapter on fornication. A true monk will be completely celibate.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Again, monks should observe total celibacy.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is an aid to overcoming gluttony but is also prescribed for those attempting to resist fornication.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribes a simple diet of foods which are "easy to prepare, cheap to purchase, and appropriate for the way of life of the brothers."

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Almost every moment of a monk's day is scheduled for either prayer or manual labor.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: There are no explicitly provided ethical precepts, but the description of how to overcome the 8 vices indicates the ethics of the ideal monastery the author is attempting to influence.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: These are mostly communal prayer, although Cassian indicates that the true monk should engage in prayer and meditation on his own between communal prayer sessions as well.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Notes: Whenever a monk is not praying with the group, he should be praying and/or contemplating on his own.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Again, daily communal prayer.

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: This is highly variable and we have no information about the monastery in Gaul to which Cassian is writing.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

Notes: There are checks on correct practice.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, Cassian's book is nothing but a check on orthopraxy. It sets the bar for the monks of Gaul based upon what Cassian remembers from his time as a monk in Egypt.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes proper monastic dress in detail as a marker of identity.

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: Monks are generally called "brother," while superiors in the monastery are called "abba" or "father."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: Monks are a separate group, focusing on prayer and spiritual attainment.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: "Famine relief" would be too grand a term. Monasteries, however, are required to give alms to the poor and to grant hospitality to strangers.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Alms for the poor are required.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: Bureaucracy at this early stage of monasticism was very simple. Each monastery generally had one superior or abbot and perhaps a bursar.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Only warfare with demonic vices.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: While simple food is mandated, how that food is produced or distributed is not addressed in this text.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Institutes of John Cassian, Cassian, John , and Boniface Ramsey, translator. The Institutes. New York: The Newman Press, 2000.

Reference: The Institutes of John Cassian, Stewart, Columba. Cassian the Monk. New York: Oxford University Press, 1999.

Reference: The Institutes of John Cassian, Rousseau, Philip . "Cassian, Contemplation, and the Cenobitic Life". *Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 26 (1975): 113-26.